

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

"ADREULA" MANDARIN IN RELATIVELY SEVERE CONDITIONS OF CITRUS CULTIVATION

Vakhtang Kobalia

*Academic Doctor of Agriculture, Emeritus,
Akaki Tsereteli State University, Kutaisi, Georgia.*

Nino Kipiani

*Academic Doctor of Agriculture, Associate Professor,
Akaki Tsereteli State University, Kutaisi, Georgia.*

Abstract

The further development of citrus growing in Georgia requires the establishment of mandarin plantations even in relatively severe conditions of crop cultivation through the introduction of appropriate varieties. The paper discusses the results of studying the fruiting and some agrobiological indicators of one of the promising varieties for this purpose - "Adreula" mandarin. The prospect of the Adreula variety in this direction is confirmed by the fact that, compared to the standard variety, it is medium-growing, ripens fruits 20-25 days earlier, has high productivity (19-21% more), and high quality indicators of fruits.

Keywords: Mandarin, variety, productivity, fruit, growth.

Introduction. Further development of citrus growing in Western Georgia, along with other agrotechnical measures, implies the further expansion of mandarin plantations in relatively severe conditions of cultivation through the selection and introduction of appropriate varieties and forms [1]; [2].

Broad-leaved Unshiu mandarin, which is the main production variety in Western Georgia, although CHARACTERIZED by relatively high frost resistance and high yield, creates problems for wide distribution in relatively harsh conditions due to late fruit ripening (November-December) - it does not manage to ripen the fruit, is easily damaged by frosts, productivity is low, etc. [3]; [4].

As for the introduced and local early varieties implemented in production (Kovano-Wase, Miyagawa-Wase, Georgian Early, and others), although they manage to ripen the fruit before the onset of harsh climatic conditions, they are characterized by low yield due to dwarf growth, as well as relatively weak frost resistance [4]; [5].

The new early mandarin variety "Adreula," studied by us in the 90s of the last century in the conditions of Abkhazia, which is medium-growing, high-yielding, and relatively frost-resistant. Appears to us as a very interesting variety in this direction [5]; [6]. Therefore, we aimed to determine some features of its growth-development and fruiting in the conditions of Kutaisi and Nosiri (Senaki district).

Material and Methodology. Mature plants of the mandarin variety "Adreula" (experimental) of nucellar origin, obtained by crossing Miyagawa-Wase mandarin with *Citrus ichangensis*, and broad-leaved Unshiu mandarin (control) were taken as the objects of research.

Observations were carried out at the experimental plots of the Scientific-Research Laboratory of Citrus Selection and Genetics of the Faculty of Agronomy of Akaki Tsereteli State University (Kutaisi) and the educational-research farm of Nosiri (Senaki district) of the same faculty. The number of plants is 15-15 units, all

grafted on *Poncirus trifoliata* rootstock and planted with a 2 x 4 m feeding area in 2013.

Phenological observations, biometric measurements, yield recording, and study of fruit quality indicators were carried out on the research plants.

Biological characteristics of plants were studied through recording and observation: early maturity - by recording changes in fruit coloration; phenological phases of plant growth and development - by generally accepted methodology; yield - by counting and weighing fruits; biochemical composition - by the method of High-Performance Liquid Chromatography. [7].

Research Results. The results of three-year (2021-2023) observations showed that, compared to the broad-leaved Unshiu mandarin, plants of the Adreula variety ripen fruits on average 20-25 days earlier on both experimental plots. They enter into bearing in the third year, i.e., one year earlier compared to the Unshiu mandarin. The average height of a 10-year-old plant of the experimental variety under Kutaisi conditions is equal to 2.05 meters, while under Nosiri conditions 2.15 meters, whereas the height of the control plant under Kutaisi conditions averages 2.45 cm, and under Nosiri conditions - 2.55 cm.

Mandarin Adreula exhibits high fruit-bearing capacity on both experimental plots. Observation of fruit bearing over three years, (Table 1) showed that 2021 was the lowest-yielding year, while 2023 was the highest-yielding. On the Kutaisi experimental plot in 2021, 358,5 kg of fruit was harvested from 15 trees of Mandarin Adreula; the productivity of one plant amounted to 303,3 units, or 23,9 kg of fruit. In the same year, 284 kg of fruit was harvested from 15 trees of Unshiu mandarin, which, calculated per plant, amounts to 252,7 units, or 18,9 kg of fruit. Thus, in 2021 the fruit-bearing of Mandarin Adreula exceeded the same indicator of the control variety by 110,6%. In 2023, the mass of fruits harvested from all plants of Mandarin Adreula amounted to 438,2 kg, and the productivity - 370,6 units and 29,2kg, respectively. In the same year, 396,0

kg of fruit was harvested from 15 trees of Unshiu mandarin. Productivity reached 357,2 units, or 26,4 kg of fruit.

Table 1

Productivity indicators of research plants by years

Name of research plants	Years of observation	Name of the experimental plot					
		Kutaisi			Nosiri		
		Yield of 15 roots	unit	kg	Yield of 15 roots	unit	kg
Mandarin Unshiu (Control)	2011	284.0	252.7	18.9	336.0	297.4	22.4
	2012	334.5	300.5	22.3	339.1	357.0	26.6
	2013	396.0	357.2	26.4	436.5	395.2	29.1
	Avg.	338.1	303.5	22.5	370.5	349.9	26.0
Mandarin Adreula (Experimental)	2011	358.5	303.3	23.9	393.1	323.2	26.2
	2012	421.5	363.9	28.1	483.1	418.7	32.2
	2013	438.2	370.6	29.2	532.5	472.1	35.5
	Avg.	406.0	346.9	27.0	469.5	404.6	31.3
% compared to control	2011	126.2	120.0	126.5	116.9	108.7	117.0
	2012	126.0	121.1	126.0	142.5	117.3	120.0
	2013	110.6	103.8	110.6	121.9	119.5	121.9
	Avg.	120.9	114.9	121.0	127.1	115.2	119.6

This year, according to fruit-bearing, the difference among the studied plants in favor of the early variety amounted to 126.0%. Based on the analysis of three-year yields, it can be said that on the **Kutaisi** experimental plot, **Mandarin Adreula** plants exhibit a higher fruit-bearing capacity than **Mandarin Unshiu** plants. In these years, the productivity of **Mandarin Adreula** was 27.0 kg, while **Mandarin Unshiu** was 22.5 kg, i.e., 121.0% more.

Almost identical results were obtained at the **Nosiri** experimental plot. If we take the three-year indicators, we will see that 15 **Mandarin Adreula** plants yield 469.5 kg of fruit, which, when calculated per plant productivity, amounts to 404.6 units, or 31.3

kg of fruit, while the same indicators for the control plant are 370.5 kg, 349.9 units, and 26.0 kg, respectively, which is 19.6% more in favor of the early variety.

Thus, on both experimental plots, the productivity of **Mandarin Adreula** plants is 19.6-21.0% higher than that of the control plants. Furthermore, if we take into account that **Mandarin Adreula** fully ripens its fruits before the onset of harsh climatic conditions, while **Mandarin Unshiu** does not manage to ripen fully, **Adreula** is unconditionally promising for establishing mandarin plantations in harsh cultivation conditions. This is also confirmed by the qualitative indicators of the fruits studied by us (Table 2).

Table 2

Mechanical and biochemical composition of the fruits of the studied plants (2023 data)

Location	Name of the studied plants	Fruit weight, g	Fruit dimensions			Fruit composition, %			Dry matter	Vitamin "C"	Acidity, %	Total sugar
			Height	Diameter	Skin	Pulp	Skin	Seed				
Kutaisi	Mandarin Adreula (Experimental)	74.2	3.9	4.7	2.2	76.9	23.1	0	11.2	34.0	0.9	6.4
	Mandarin Unshiu (Control)	72.9	3.8	4.5	2.2	75.5	24.5	0	10.6	31.2	1.1	6.2
Nosiri	Mandarin Adreula (Experimental)	77.8	4.0	4.7	2.3	77.2	22.8	0	11.5	33.2	0.9	6.5

Location	Name of the studied plants	Fruit weight, g	Fruit dimensions			Fruit composition, %			Dry matter	Vitamin "C"	Acidity, %	Total sugar
			Height	Diameter	Skin	Pulp	Skin	Seed				
	Mandarin Unshiu (Control)	74.0	4.0	4.6	2.3	75.9	24.1	0	10.7	32.3	1.1	6.2

From the mechanical and biochemical analysis of the fruits of the studied plants, it appears that **Mandarin Adreula** fruits are distinguished by high indicators in this regard on both experimental plots. Specifically, the fruit mass in **Kutaisi** conditions averages 74.2 g, while in **Nosiri** conditions it is 77.8 g, whereas in 'Unshiu' it is equal to 72.9 and 74.2 g, respectively. The pulp yield in the fruits of the experimental variety is 76.9% and 77.2% according to the plots, while in the control it is 75.5% and 75.9%. The fruits of all plants are seedless. In 'Adreula' fruit, dry matter constitutes 11.2-11.5%, Vitamin "C" 33.2-34.0 mg/100g, acidity 0.9%, and total sugars 6.4-6.5%. All these indicators are much better than in the fruits of 'Unshiu' mandarin.

Conclusion. Based on the above, it can be concluded that in relatively harsh conditions of mandarin cultivation, the early mandarin variety 'Adreula' is more promising, which is medium-growing, ripens fruits 20-25 days earlier compared to the broad-leaved 'Unshiu' mandarin, enters bearing one year earlier, and their productivity is 19.6-20.0% higher; also, the qualitative indicators of the fruits are the best.

References

1. Baratashvili, Khalvashi 2016: D. Baratashvili, N. Khalvashi. Biological diversity and genetic resources of citrus in Georgia. Publishing House "Batumi Shota Rustaveli State University", Batumi, 2016, pp. 234-289.
2. Jobava T., Kobalia V. 2007. Lemon Dioskuria and Mandarin Adreula-promising selection varieties.

Bulletin of the Academy of Agricultural Sciences of Georgia, Vol. 20, Tbilisi, 2007, pp. 94-96.

3. Kipiani N., Tutberidze B. 2010. Perspectives of practical use of distant hybrids of citrus plants. Subtropical Crops, 2010, No. 1-4, pp. 23-27.

4. Kobalia V. 2016. "Results of the study of biomorphological and economic indicators of the diversity of forms of nucellar seedlings of 'Adreula' MANDARIN". Periodic Scientific Journal **AgroNEWS**, No. 1, 2016, 42-47

5. Nino Davit Kipiani „The Emergence of Hybrid Seeds and Polyembryony in Some Citrus Cultigens” JLS „Journal of Life Sciences”. Volume 8, Number 7, July 2014 ISSN 1934-7391 (Print) ISSN 1934-7405 (Online) David Publishing company. www.davidpublishing.com. Impact Factor New York, NY 10034, USA (Aims and Scope)Pg. 603-604

6. Roland Kopaliani*, Nino Kipiani*, Shorena Kapanadze*, Julieta Sanikidze „Some Aspects of Growth and Development of Hybrid Citrus Seedlings Obtained through Distant Hybridization ISSN - 0132 – 1447

<http://science.org.ge/bnas/vol-19-2.html>

<http://science.org.ge/moambe/moambe-geo.html> VOL 19 N2 2025 139-141 science.org.ge

7. Kobalia V. 2018. Biochemical characterization of promising clones of early mandarin. Bulletin of the Academy of Agricultural Sciences of Georgia, No. 21(40), Tb., 2018, pp. 51-54.